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In ovo model showing high angiogenesis potential of electrospun chitosan based multilayered scaffold for urethral repair

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Introduction: Several congenital and acquired injuries of the urethral spongiosum, including trauma, instrumentation, and infection, can result in scar formation of ultimately urethral stricture (1). However, in hypospadias, the distal blood supply of the spongiosum is compromised, particularly in severe phenotypes of this pathology or in repeat surgeries. Although several surgical techniques were introduced to manage failed hypospadias repair, this is considered a challenging clinical problem where scarring and hypovascular tissues exist (2). Chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) is used in tissue engineering to test growth factors and biocompatibility materials and test these factors' capacity to provoke new blood vessels from established vasculature.

Methods: To compare differently fabricated scaffolds in terms of vascularization, the constructs were tested in the CAM assay with subsequent vascular development and biocompatibility assessment.

Results & Discussions: Vascularization induced by Chitosan Based Multilayered Scaffold led to a vessel distribution more homogenous and highly dense adjacent to the constructs, while SIS scaffold enhanced vessel density to a significantly lower extent. Inadequate angiogenesis and epithelialization make urethral regeneration using conventional tissue-engineered grafts a significant challenge.

Conclusions: Electrospun Chitosan Based Multilayered Scaffold shows potential to function as a tissue-engineered urethra graft with excellent angiogenesis to maintain epithelialization and urethral regeneration in ovo. The CAM assay is an easy and cheap screening tool for the angiogenic properties of such scaffolds.

Key words: *Angiogenesis, CAM assay, Chitosan, Urethral Repair*

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